

Preliminary Development of the EPS_N Transport Code Based on deal.II

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ABSTRACT

High-fidelity reactor core simulation requires accurate geometric modeling and rigorous neutron transport calculations. Traditional 2-D/1-D deterministic transport methods have limited capability in representing detailed axial core geometry, while the Monte Carlo method, despite its high accuracy, remains constrained in engineering applications due to its substantial computational cost and challenges in obtaining global solution statistics efficiently. This study presents a second-order transport code designed for efficient solution on multi-dimensional unstructured meshes. The code solves the Even-parity S_N equation using finite element spatial discretization. Since the coupling between discrete angles only occurs through the scattering term on the right-hand side of the equation, classical source iteration can be employed as the solution strategy. The correctness of the transport solver under the P_0 scattering approximation is verified by comparing its numerical solution to the OECD NEACRP-L-336 benchmark problem against Monte-Carlo reference solution. Future work will focus on extending the support for high-order scattering.

Keywords: unstructured grids, finite element method, Even-parity S_N , deal.II, neutron transport

1. INTRODUCTION

With the rapid advancement of modern computing power, the continuous exploitation of reactor design margins, and the emergence of innovative reactor concepts, high-fidelity numerical simulation of core neutron physics has become increasingly important in reactor core design and safety analysis. High-fidelity neutron physics calculations can be pursued from two complementary perspectives. The first concerns the mathematical model, namely replacing diffusion approximations with more rigorous transport models, such as the S_N , P_N , method of characteristics (MOC), and Monte-Carlo methods [1]. The second involves the geometric model, which requires accurate representation of complex core structures using refined and flexible computational meshes. The application of Monte Carlo method in routine engineering design remains limited by its high computational cost and difficulties in obtaining global solution statistics. Traditional 2-D/1-D deterministic methods, despite of vastly improved computational efficiency relative to Monte-Carlo, rely on axial stretching prism geometry approximations that make it difficult to accurately describe geometric variation along the axial direction [2]. To overcome these limitations, this study develops a second-order transport code capable of efficiently solving neutron transport problems on fully three-dimensional unstructured meshes. The transport formulation is based on the classical even-parity S_N equations [3]. This approach transforms the original first-order (in space) form of the Boltzmann transport equation into an equivalent second-order form through algebraic manipulation, and solves it along a set of discrete angular directions using the discrete ordinates method. Since angular fluxes in different directions are coupled only through the scattering source term, the formulation enables the use of the well-established source iteration method, together with various iterative acceleration techniques.

The second-order S_N transport equation [4] boasts two significant advantages over the first-order equation. Firstly, the number of angular unknowns is halved; secondly, the equation takes on an elliptic

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form, which can be efficiently solved using the continuous finite element method as is the case for diffusion equation, with native supports for unstructured meshes. Unlike existing even-parity S_N code such as DANTE and PROTEUS-SN2ND, the code in discussion was developed using deal.II finite element framework [5] for spatial discretization. The deal.II framework is a C++ library for solving partial differential equations which provides fine-grained control over the code implementation. The main technical features of deal.II include: 1) Almost dimension independent coding through utilization of C++ templates for dimension variable; 2) Well-rounded tools set for adaptive mesh refinement; 3) Support for a variety of finite element types, including continuous/discontinuous Lagrange elements of any order, Nedelec and Raviart-Thomas elements of any order, etc.; 4) Support for massive parallelization through Threading Build Block and MPI, and so on. Besides, with built-in mesh refinement toolkit, the code can adjust spatial resolution on demand or in an adaptive-mesh-refinement style.

2. THEORETICAL METHODS

This study adopts the deal.II finite element framework to perform space discretization and solve the Even-parity S_N transport equation using first-order continuous finite elements. Specifically, for the steady-state reactor core neutronics analysis in the form of a multi-group eigenvalue problems was considered. This section provides a detailed introduction to the mathematical model adopted as well as the iterative solution process.

2.1. Even-parity S_N Multi-Group Eigenvalue Equation

The first-order mono-energetic steady-state Boltzmann neutron transport equation has the following form:

$$\vec{\Omega} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \psi(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega}) + \sigma_t(\vec{r}) \psi(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega}) = Q(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega}), \quad (1)$$

where $Q(\vec{\Omega})$ is the source term composed of both the scattering source and the external source (S_{ext}), σ represents the macroscopic cross-section. By expanding the scattering term using spherical harmonics, we obtain:

$$Q(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega}) = \mathcal{K}_s \psi + S_{\text{ext}} = \sum_{l=0}^L \sum_{q=-l}^l \frac{2l+1}{4\pi} \sigma_{s,l}(\vec{r}) \Phi_l^q(\vec{r}) Y_l^q(\vec{\Omega}) + S_{\text{ext}}(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega}). \quad (2)$$

In a neutron multiplying medium, the external source is replaced by the fission source, and the original equation is transformed into an eigenvalue problem by introducing the effective multiplication coefficient k_{eff} :

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{\Omega} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \psi(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega}) + \sigma_t(\vec{r}) \psi(\vec{r}, \vec{\Omega}) &= \mathcal{K}_s \psi + \frac{S_f}{k_{\text{eff}}} \\ &= \sum_{l=0}^L \sum_{q=-l}^l \frac{2l+1}{4\pi} \sigma_{s,l}(\vec{r}) \Phi_l^q(\vec{r}) Y_l^q(\vec{\Omega}) + \frac{1}{4\pi \cdot k_{\text{eff}}} \nu \sigma_f(\vec{r}) \Phi_0(\vec{r}). \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

By defining the odd- and even-parity angular flux and source terms (for brevity, the spatial dependency on \vec{r} is dropped in the following equations):

$$\psi^\pm(\vec{\Omega}) = \frac{1}{2} [\psi(\vec{\Omega}) \pm \psi(-\vec{\Omega})], \quad (4)$$

$$Q^\pm(\vec{\Omega}) = \frac{1}{2} [Q(\vec{\Omega}) \pm Q(-\vec{\Omega})], \quad (5)$$

the original first-order equation can be split into even-parity equations and odd-parity equations:

$$\vec{\Omega} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \psi^- + \sigma_t \psi^+ = Q^+, \quad (6)$$

$$\vec{\Omega} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \psi^+ + \sigma_t \psi^- = Q^-. \quad (7)$$

Substitute the Equation (7) into Equation (6) to eliminate the ψ^- term and obtain:

$$-\vec{\Omega} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \frac{1}{\sigma_t} \vec{\Omega} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \psi^+ + \sigma_t \psi^+ = Q^+ - \vec{\Omega} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \frac{Q^-}{\sigma_t}. \quad (8)$$

Equation (8) can be further written in the multi-group form for energy-dependent problems:

$$-\vec{\Omega} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \frac{1}{\sigma_{t,g}} \vec{\Omega} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \psi_g^+ + \sigma_{t,g} \psi_g^+ = Q_g^+ - \vec{\Omega} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \frac{Q_g^-}{\sigma_t}, \quad g = 1 \cdots G \quad (9)$$

where

$$Q_g(\vec{\Omega}) = \sum_{g'=0}^G \sum_{l=0}^L \sum_{q=-l}^l \frac{2l+1}{4\pi} \sigma_{s,l,g' \rightarrow g} \Phi_{l,g'}^q Y_l^q(\vec{\Omega}) + \frac{1}{4\pi \cdot k_{\text{eff}}} \chi_g \sum_{g'=0}^G \nu \sigma_{f,g'} \Phi_{0,g'}. \quad (10)$$

For the purpose of preliminary methodology verification, this paper only considers isotropic scattering (P_0), that is $\sigma_{s,l,g' \rightarrow g} = 0$ for $l > 0$. Under this assumption, Q_g^+ and Q_g^- degenerates into:

$$Q_g^+(\vec{\Omega}) = \sum_{g'=0}^G \frac{1}{4\pi} \sigma_{s,0,g' \rightarrow g} \Phi_{0,g'} Y_0 + \frac{1}{4\pi \cdot k_{\text{eff}}} \chi_g \sum_{g'=0}^G \nu \sigma_{f,g'} \cdot \Phi_{0,g'}, \quad (11)$$

$$Q_g^-(\vec{\Omega}) = 0. \quad (12)$$

Substituting Equation (11) and Equation (12) into Equation (9), and adopting discrete ordinate method in angle, we obtain:

$$-\vec{\Omega} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \frac{1}{\sigma_{t,g}} \vec{\Omega} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \psi_{g,m}^+ + \sigma_{t,g} \psi_{g,m}^+ = \frac{1}{4\pi} \sum_{g'=0}^G \left(\sigma_{s,0,g' \rightarrow g} \Phi_{0,g'} + \frac{\chi_g}{k_{\text{eff}}} \nu \sigma_{f,g'} \Phi_{0,g'} \right), \quad m = 1 \cdots M \quad (13)$$

where m is the directional index and the scalar flux is the weighted sum of discrete angular fluxes:

$$\Phi_{0,g} = \sum_{m=1}^M w_m^+ \psi_{g,m}^+, \quad g = 1 \cdots G. \quad (14)$$

In this study, the discretization angle collocation is based on the Gauss-Legendre-Chebyshev quadrature set [6], that is, the polar cosines is determined by Gauss-Legendre quadrature points, where the

azimuth angle dictated by Chebychev quadrature points. For the S_N method in the form of a first-order equation, the total number of discrete directions M is $N(N+2)$. However, for the Even-parity S_N method, thanks to the angular symmetry of ψ^\pm , it suffices to only compute for the discrete directions of half a sphere, that is, $M = N(N+2)/2$.

2.1.1. Iterative solution strategy

For the multi-group eigenvalue problem, this program adopts a solution method combining outer power iteration and inner source iteration. That is, between different energy groups, power iteration is used to converge the eigenvalue k_{eff} and the multi-group scalar fluxes; within each energy group, source iteration is performed to converge the angular fluxes of each discrete direction. In the source iteration stage, the fission source term and the in-scatter neutron source from other energy groups are considered as fixed, whose values depends on the scalar flux values from the previous outer power iteration. To accelerate convergence, the calculation of the fixed source in source iteration can also use the latest update of the scalar flux values within the current power iteration, which is the actual scheme adopted in this program. A pseudo-code is given below for illustrative purpose:

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{ $\Phi_{0,g}$ } = 1.0, { $\psi_{g,m}^+$ } = 1.0    //initialize scalar flux and angular flux
 $k_{\text{eff}} = 1.0$                        //initialize effective multiplication factor
repeat                               //power iteration over energy groups
  for  $g$  in 1... $G$ 
    repeat                             //within-group source iteration over angles
      for  $m$  in 1... $M$ :
        compute RHS due to within-group scattering using latest  $\Phi_{0,g}$ 
        compute RHS due to cross-group scattering and fission using last iterate of { $\Phi_{0,g'}^{\text{old}}$ } $g' \neq g$ 
        inverse  $S_N$  transport equation along direction  $m$  to solve for  $\psi_{g,m}^+$ 
      end for
       $\Phi_{0,g} \leftarrow \sum w_m^+ \psi_{g,m}^+$ 
    until  $\|\Phi_{0,g} - \Phi_{0,g}^{\text{old}}\| / \|\Phi_{0,g}^{\text{old}}\| < \text{tol}_{\text{SI}}$  //check for source iteration convergence
  end for
   $k_{\text{eff}} \leftarrow \sum_{g'=1}^G \nu \sigma_{f,g'} \Phi_{0,g'}$ 
  { $\Phi_{0,g}^{\text{old}}$ }  $\leftarrow$  { $\Phi_{0,g}$ } /  $k_{\text{eff}}$ 
until  $|k_{\text{eff}} - k_{\text{eff}}^{\text{old}}| / k_{\text{eff}} < \text{tol}_{k_{\text{eff}}}$  //check for power iteration convergence
output { $\psi_{g,m}^+$ }, { $\Phi_{0,g}$ }, and  $k_{\text{eff}}$ .

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3. NUMERICAL VERIFICATION

To verify the efficacy of the algorithm and its implementation, numerical verification was performed based on the NEACRP-L-336 benchmark problem published by OECD/NEA [7]. Comparison against multi-group Monte-Carlo simulation results are presented here.

3.1. Problem Description

NEACRP-L-336 benchmark problem is a two-dimensional two-group eigenvalue problem. It models a fictional reactor core with a 4×4 layout composed of PWR fuel assemblies. Two UOX assemblies and two MOX assemblies are arranged in a checkerboard pattern, surrounded by a vacuum boundary. The benchmark problem simulates 1/4 of the core (2×2 assemblies) in characterization of the full core

by setting reflective boundary conditions on the east and the north, together with vacuum boundary conditions on the west and the south. The fuel assembly lattice and 1/4-core layout are shown in Figure 1. In the MOX assembly, fuel rods with three different compositions are loaded from the center to the peripheral. All fuel rods, control rods, guided tubes, and fission chambers are homogenized within each lattice. Table 1 provides the cross-section data of all involved materials and their corresponding legend symbols. Since this benchmark problem was originally intended for verifying the core diffusion calculation codes, fast group and thermal group diffusion coefficients (D_1 and D_2) were specified in the original problem statement, while in-group scattering cross-sections which do not show up in the diffusion equation were omitted. In this study, to perform consistent transport calculations, the in-group scattering cross-sections ($\sigma_{s,1 \rightarrow 1}^*$ and $\sigma_{s,2 \rightarrow 2}^*$) are inferred from the original material data, which are also tabulated in Table I.

Figure 1. The OECD-NEACRP-L-336 benchmark fuel assembly lattice and core layout.

Table I. OECD-NEACRP-L-336 benchmark problem material cross-section data.

	Legend	D_1	$\sigma_{a,1}$	$\nu\sigma_{f,1}$	$\sigma_{s,1 \rightarrow 2}$	D_2	$\sigma_{a,2}$	$\nu\sigma_{f,2}$	$\sigma_{s,1 \rightarrow 1}^*$	$\sigma_{s,2 \rightarrow 2}^*$
UO2	U	1.2	0.010	0.0050	0.020	0.4	0.1	0.125	0.248	0.733
MOX(1)	M1	1.2	0.015	0.0075	0.015	0.4	0.2	0.300	0.248	0.633
MOX(2)	M2	1.2	0.015	0.0075	0.015	0.4	0.25	0.375	0.248	0.583
MOX(3)	M3	1.2	0.015	0.0075	0.015	0.4	0.30	0.450	0.248	0.533
Guide Tube	X	1.2	0.001	0	0.025	0.4	0.02	0	0.252	0.813
Fission Chamber	C	1.2	0.001	0	0.025	0.4	0.02	0	0.252	0.813

3.2. Test Results

The EPS_N transport calculations were performed with varying order of angular quadratures (S_2 , S_4 , and S_8) over a hierarchy of uniformly refined meshes (R_0 , R_1 , and R_2 , where R_0 represent the coarse mesh corresponding to the lattice grid, R_1 means the coarse mesh refined once, etc.). Owing to the axial symmetry of the two-dimensional problem, the number of quadrature points is further halved (e.g. 6 in the case of S_4). The convergence tolerance for both the internal source iteration and the external power iteration is set to 10^{-5} (relative error). In this paper, we adopt a Monte-Carlo simulation result as the

ground truth to verify out EPS_N code. The Monte-Carlo simulation was performed using the RMC code[8], which was developed by Tsinghua University as a high-fidelity modeling tool dedicated for reactor analyses. Scalar flux distributions for fast and thermal group together with k_{eff} were output by RMC as the reference solutions.

Figure 2, Figure 3, and Figure 4 respectively show the thermal group and fast group neutron flux distributions obtained by Even-parity S_N and RMC calculations, as well as the relative differences between the two. Both thermal fluxes and fast fluxes are renormalized as such that total flux with group sums to 1.0. The EPS_N results plotted here were computed with S_8-R_2 , while the RMC reference solutions were obtained using 640,000 particles/batch with 50 active batches, resulting in a k_{eff} standard deviation of 10 pcm. The RMC flux distribution was obtained by tallying scalar flux over each lattice cell.

Figure 2, Figure 3 shows that EPS_N and RMC yields consistent flux distribution profiles for both thermal and fast neutrons. A close inspection on Figure 4 tells that for thermal flux, the difference occurs mainly within the MOX fuel rods and on the outer boundary, whereas for fast flux, the difference appears mostly on the outer vacuum boundary. For both thermal and fast fluxes, the maximum lattice-averaged error is within 4%. Table II compares the results for several key metrics, including k_{eff} , the fast-to-thermal flux ratio, and the relative error on L2-norm for both thermal and fast group. It can be inferred from the tabulate results that the EPS_N solution converges to the RMC solution as angular and spatial resolution increase. For the most refined case (S_8-R_2), the k_{eff} deviation is 11 pcm, and thermal flux and fast flux relative L2-error are around 0.37% and 0.23% respectively.

Figure 2. Thermal neutron flux comparison.

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper introduces a multi-group neutronics eigenvalue calculation program based on the Even-parity S_N second-order transport method, which can be used for efficient and high-precision reactor physics calculations for complex core structures. The correctness of the code was verified against high-precision Monte-Carlo simulation in solving the NEACRP-L-336 benchmark problem released by OECD/NEA. With reasonable angular and spatial refinement, the EPS_N code converged towards the Monte-Carlo reference solution with satisfactory consistency. Being in its early development stage, the code was only tested in 2-D with isotropic scattering and computational efficiency was not reported due

Figure 3. Fast neutron flux comparison.

Figure 4. Spatial distribution of scalar flux relative difference ($|EPS_N - RMC| / \frac{|EPS_N + RMC|}{2}$).

Table II. OECD-NEACRP-L-336 benchmark problem key-metrics comparison results.

	k_{eff}	Δk_{eff}	fast-to-thermal flux ratio	Δ flux ratio	thermal group rel. L2-error	fast group rel. L2-error
RMC	0.91803	(0.00010)	6.906	–	–	–
S_2 - R_1	0.91689	0.00114	6.913	0.007	2.0084%	1.4885%
S_4 - R_1	0.91811	0.00008	6.924	0.018	0.9499%	0.4564%
S_8 - R_1	0.91821	0.00018	6.925	0.019	0.7700%	0.3090%
S_8 - R_2	0.91792	0.00011	6.914	0.008	0.3676%	0.2303%

to lack of optimization. By leveraging the dimension-independent coding paradigm adopted by deal.II framework, it can be easily extended to 3-D. Anisotropic scattering will be implemented in further development.

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REFERENCES

- [1] Y. Zhang, J. C. Ragusa, and J. E. Morel. "Model Error Estimation for the Simplified PN Radiation Transport Equations." *Nuclear Science and Engineering*, **volume 194**(10), pp. 903–926 (2020).
- [2] Y. S. Jung, C. Lee, and M. A. Smith. "PROTEUS-MOC user manual." Technical report, Argonne National Lab.(ANL), Argonne, IL (United States) (2018).
- [3] J. E. Morel, B. T. Adams, T. Noh, J. M. McGhee, T. M. Evans, and T. J. Urbatsch. "Spatial discretizations for self-adjoint forms of the radiative transfer equations." *Journal of Computational Physics*, **volume 214**(1), pp. 12–40 (2006).
- [4] E. E. Lewis. "Second-order neutron transport methods." In *Nuclear Computational Science: A Century in Review*, pp. 85–115. Springer (2009).
- [5] D. Arndt, W. Bangerth, M. Bergbauer, B. Blais, M. Fehling, R. Gassmüller, T. Heister, L. Heltai, M. Kronbichler, M. Maier, et al. "The deal. II library, version 9.7." *Journal of Numerical Mathematics* (2025).
- [6] W. F. Walters. "Use of the Chebyshev-Legendre quadrature set in discrete-ordinate codes." Technical report, Los Alamos National Laboratory (LANL), Los Alamos, NM (United States) (1987).
- [7] C. Cavarec, J. Perron, D. Verwaerde, J. West, et al. "Benchmark calculations of power distribution within assemblies." Technical report, Nuclear Energy Agency, 75-Paris (France) (1994).
- [8] K. Wang, Z. Li, D. She, J. G. Liang, Q. Xu, Y. Qiu, others, and G. Yu. "RMC—A Monte Carlo code for reactor core analysis." *Annals of Nuclear Energy*, **volume 82**, pp. 121–129 (2015).